

Technical Architecture of Terminology Services 4 NFDI (TS4NFDI)

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background information

Terminologies play a critical role in semantically linking research data across disciplines. They provide the basis for consensus definitions of concepts, thereby ensuring conceptual alignment, even when the nomenclature differs between domains. The use of standardized terminologies promotes interoperability and data integration, as data described through common terminologies can be understood and used across different sources and disciplines significantly improving their reusability. Currently, NFDI consortia are working with terminologies at different stages of maturity and FAIRness.

A number of technically mature terminology services and repositories are publicly available. Terminology registries such as the Basic Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications (BARTOC) represent the simplest form of such a service [1]. Registries typically list comprehensive metadata about vocabularies, terminologies and ontologies and link to their original source. Terminology repositories contain full terminology data in machine-readable form and, in addition, provide access to their data via APIs [2].

Well-used open-source terminology service frameworks like OntoPortal [3] and Ontology Lookup Service (OLS) [4] offer extended features for searching and browsing

within the hosted terminologies and provide visualization of hierarchical relationships in so-called tree views as well as information about concepts and properties. OntoPortal is a portal architecture developed by the OntoPortal Alliance [5] that can be customized for a domain to provide discipline-specific advanced semantic repositories. It has evolved from BioPortal, which provides access to a large collection of biomedical ontologies and terminologies [6]. The Ontology Lookup Service, developed and hosted at the EMBL European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), provides ontology search and visualization services as well as data access and search via an API [4]. There is also Skosmos, an open-source web-based browser and publishing tool [7] specialized for Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) vocabularies [8]. It provides a user interface for browsing and searching the data as well as Linked Data access with APIs that support term-based searches. Further terminology services include DANTE (with JSKOS API) [9] or the Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV) (with SPARQL API) [10], the General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus (GEMET) [11], the GND (Gemeinsame Normdatei) [12] and the geographical database GeoNames [13] in the NFDI landscape and beyond.

1.2 What is TS4NFDI?

Terminology Services 4 NFDI (TS4NFDI) aims to standardize and harmonize collaborative terminology management within the NFDI. The development of the cross-domain basic service TS4NFDI for the provision, curation, development, harmonization, and mapping of terminologies is funded by Base4NFDI, a joint consortium of all 26 subject consortia of NFDI. TS4NFDI is currently in the initialization phase. By the end of this phase (end of Q4/2024), TS4NFDI will provide a centralized and harmonized API Gateway along with a Terminology Service Suite (TSS). The TSS will feature JavaScript-based Graphical User Interface (GUI) widgets that provide direct access to at least three different terminology service software stacks: Ontoportal, Skosmos, and Ontology Lookup Service. These software stacks, available across multiple instances, will be integrated into a unified terminology service access point for web services.

2. TS4NFDI Architecture and Core Components

The TS4NFDI architecture is centered around a flexible, service-based approach that enables seamless integration of external terminology services, offering a centralized and unified access point for all TS4NFDI users via dedicated applications. In the following sections we describe the key components that comprise the system as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overview of the TS4NFDI Architecture. The overall architecture is divided into four layers. The uppermost layer comprises applications utilizing TS4NFDI. These independent (web)services with interfaces or (research)programs represent various use cases. The second layer from the top contains the TS4NFDI Service Portal, which comprises the Terminology Service Suite, the Incubator Dashboard, the frontend of the TS4NFDI Mapping Service and a Configuration Panel. The penultimate layer is constituted by the API Gateway, which comprises service wrappers and the associated service databases. The final layer provides details on the backend of the TS4NFDI Mapping Service and multiple terminology services. These terminology services have the potential to be hosted by third parties or alternatively by the project institutions of TS4NFDI.

2.1 TS4NFDI Service Portal

TS4NFDI aims to support different scientific communities and their various use cases and downstream services. TS4NFDI therefore wants to enable consortia and users to put together customised and individually tailored configurations of the basic service via a graphical user interface. To facilitate the integration and customisation of the features of TS4NFDI into the services of the NFDI consortia, TS4NFDI will provide a central TS4NFDI Service Portal. The TS4NFDI Service Portal is designed to facilitate the creation and management of entity sets and terminology collections (see Figure 3a). This enables domain experts to configure the response of the centralized API Gateway or the Terminology Service Suite (TSS) following their specific requirements. To enable customisation, an administrator user interface will be provided within a configuration panel, utilising the widgets provided by the Terminology Service Suite (see 2.1.1). This will ensure simple access and enhance usability for administrators. The configuration panel will display a comprehensive list of all available terminologies from the various terminology services accessed by the API Gateway. Furthermore, it is possible to list terminologies that are subject to licence restrictions. Should a user meet the licence conditions, these terminologies can also be utilised via the widgets. Next to this, a Mapping Service will be also accessible via the TS4NFDI Service Portal. To implement these access-restricted areas or licenced terminologies the features of the basic service IAM4NFDI will be used. The TS4NFDI Service Portal will also integrate the TSS from WP5, and will provide documentation of the TS4NFDI Incubator Projects in an incubator project dashboard.

2.1.1 Terminology Service Suite

TS4NFDI will provide modular graphical user interface (GUI) widgets in the Terminology Service Suite (TSS) that facilitate the seamless integration of terminology functionalities into service interfaces. These widgets are designed to streamline the development of terminology service interfaces by providing ready-to-use components for tasks such as term search, ontology browsing, and semantic annotation. The Terminology Service Suite (TSS) is thus defined as a collection of interactive, web-based widgets designed to facilitate the integration of terminology service

functions into third-party applications. The modular and configurable nature of these widgets allows consortia to effortlessly integrate terminology functionalities directly into their platforms, significantly reducing development efforts. As an example, platforms that require data annotation, such as data repositories, could integrate the widgets of the TSS enabling their users to find the right terms to annotate the data.

The widgets are built using React and TypeScript and can be used in both React and plain HTML applications. The functionality and arguments are the same for the React and plain HTML versions. By providing ready-to-use UI components, TS4NFDI reduces the complexity of integrating semantic information into NFDI platforms. This includes widgets for browsing ontologies, performing term lookups, and visualizing mappings between concepts.

The widgets are designed to work seamlessly across different underlying terminology services via the TS4NFDI API Gateway, supporting the integration of both domain-specific and cross-domain terminologies.

2.1.2 TS4NFDI Mapping Service

A crucial component of the TS4NFDI system will be the NFDI-wide Mapping Service, which facilitates cross-domain interoperability by enabling the alignment of terminologies from different disciplines. The mappings will be based on the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM), ensuring that mappings are shared and accessible in a standard format across the NFDI community.

The Mapping Service allows users to create, manage, and retrieve mappings between terms from different vocabularies or ontologies. These mappings enable the discovery of semantic equivalences and relationships across disciplines, fostering a more integrated understanding of domain-specific knowledge.

The software Cocoda was selected for the NFDI-wide mapping service. Cocoda is published under a MIT license on GitHub¹ and is based on Vue.js.

¹ <https://github.com/gbv/cocoda>

The TS4NFDI Mapping Service will support both automated and manual curation of mappings. Automated mapping processes will suggest potential correspondences, while domain experts can manually validate or refine these mappings to ensure high quality.

The TS4NFDI Mapping Service can also integrate upper-level ontologies, allowing more refined cross-disciplinary mappings by aligning domain-specific terminologies with shared conceptual models.

Cross-domain mappings will be maintained in a centralized repository, allowing users to access mappings on-demand or as part of broader data integration efforts. The use of SSSOM as a standard format will ensure that mappings are interoperable and can be easily shared across platforms.

2.1.3 Incubator Dashboard

The Incubator Dashboard will provide a comprehensive list of all third-party services/partners that have collaborated with TS4NFDI in the context of an incubator. It will provide an overview of each specific incubator project. This will include a description of the incubator, the goals of the incubator project, the incubator project's status, the outcomes of the incubator project (e.g. scientific publications), and a reference to the activity page.

2.2 API Gateway

The API Gateway serves as the principal interface between users and the connected (Web) interfaces, as well as the various central or federated terminology services. In this capacity, it functions as a unifying and centralized access point for all requests pertaining to terminology, providing a cohesive API for accessing and managing terminologies across diverse domains. This ensures a standardised and harmonised interface, facilitating streamlined operations. The functionalities offered by the API Gateway are as follows:

- **Standardized API Access:** The API Gateway abstracts the complexity of the underlying terminology services, enabling users to access multiple service APIs

through a common one without needing to understand the specificities of each service. This includes operations such as searching, suggesting, and retrieving information about terms, terminologies, or mappings.

- **Cross-Domain Support:** The API Gateway will provide access to cross-domain terminologies and mappings, allowing users to explore and map concepts across multiple disciplines. This supports more effective inter-disciplinary collaboration and data interoperability within the NFDI community.
- **Routing and Load Balancing:** The API Gateway manages the routing of incoming requests to the appropriate services, including load balancing to ensure efficient resource usage and optimal performance for high-traffic requests.

The API Gateway is built using Java.

2.2.1 Service Wrappers

To facilitate the integration of existing terminology services, generic service wrappers will be developed. These wrappers are designed to interface with multiple types of standard terminology technologies, including OLS [4], OntoPortal [5], and Skosmos [7], among others. These wrappers will act as adapters that allow these platforms to communicate with the TS4NFDI API Gateway through a unified protocol.

The wrappers provide a layer of abstraction that handles differences in data formats, communication protocols, and API specifications between various terminology services. The purpose of the standardisation of requests and responses in the service wrappers is to ensure compatibility for the central API Gateway.

The following Terminology Service Technologies are supported:

- **Ontology Lookup Service (OLS):** A service for managing and looking up ontologies. The wrapper ensures that TS4NFDI users can access and integrate OLS-based terminology services, like TIB Terminology Service, SemLookP, or EMBL-EBIs OLS.
- **OntoPortal:** Widely used for hosting ontology repositories. The TS4NFDI OntoPortal wrapper allows seamless interaction with OntoPortal systems, like the NFDI4Biodiversity BioPortal [6], BiodivPortal, or AgroPortal. Functionalities

include: search, text annotation, ontology and term information retrieval, and additional ontology management functionalities like versioning and automatic release updates.

- Skosmos: A web-based platform for publishing controlled vocabularies in SKOS format. The wrapper translates Skosmos-based queries into the unified API format, allowing the use of thesauri and other structured vocabularies hosted on Skosmos within TS4NFDI, such as BARTOC Skosmos, Thesaurus for the Social Sciences (TheSoz), ZPID Vocabularies, and ZBW classifications.

The design of the wrappers is designed to be extensible, meaning it can easily be adapted to integrate additional terminology services as needed. This modularity ensures future scalability and the ability to incorporate other systems that are in use or may emerge within the NFDI or external partners. OLS, OntoPortal and Skosmos were chosen based on their widespread use within NFDI communities, the diversity of their underlying technologies, and the availability of expertise among project partners.

2.2.2 Service Databases

The required data for user management will be stored in the API Gateway service databases. Concurrently, collections of terminologies will be stored with the objective of enhancing functionality for terminology services. Finally, the required information for entity sets will be maintained and saved in the service databases.

2.3 Single sign-on via IAM4NFDI authentication service

Moreover, the integration of the functionality of the IAM4NFDI basic service enables TS4NFDI to track and acknowledge contributions to terminology curation across all services via a single sign-on (SSO). Furthermore, the integration of the TS4NFDI architecture also provides controlled access to terminologies with licence restrictions. The SSO will interact with at least 4 different components of the TS4NFDI Architecture: 1) the TS4NFDI Service Portal, 2) the widgets of Terminology Service Suite, 3) the TS4NFDI Mapping Service, and 4) the API Gateway (depicted in Figure 2).

Figure 2: The following figure illustrates the interaction of the single sign-on of the IAM4NFDI usage with the different components of TS4NFDI.

3. Current Status

3.1. TS4NFDI Service Portal

The functionality of the TS4NFDI Service Portal was designed through the requirements of the participants of the after the The development of the TS4NFDI Service Portal started in Q1/2025 in the integration phase of TS4NFDI. A first prototype of the TS4NFDI Service Portal was provided at the end of Q1/2025. The source code of the TS4NFDI Service Portal is accessible via GitHub².

3.1.1 Terminology Service Suite

A first version of the Terminology Service Suite was published in Q2/2024. It was continuously extended during the initialisation phase. At this moment it contains widget for The source code of the the TSS is accessible via Github³. The documentation⁴ of the TSS is handled via a Storybook⁵. Storybook is an open source tool for developing, documenting, and maintaining user interface components for React, Vue, Angular, and other frameworks. The TSS Storybook is divided into three sections: 1) Overview, 2) React, and 3) HTML:

² <https://github.com/ts4nfdi/service-portal/>

³ <https://github.com/ts4nfdi/terminology-service-suite>

⁴ <https://ts4nfdi.github.io/terminology-service-suite/comp/latest/>

⁵ <https://storybook.js.org/>

- The Overview section provides an overview of the TSS and the manner in which its widgets can be utilised.
- The React section, on the other hand, encompasses the various widgets and their corresponding documentation.
- Finally, the HTML section is similar to the React section in that it also contains the different widgets and their documentation.

The Autocomplete Widget was selected as a proof of concept to interact with the API Gateway. The results obtained demonstrated the feasibility of conducting searches across three distinct software stacks: OLS, OntoPortal and Skosmos. In addition, the hierarchy widget was selected as a proof of concept to demonstrate the capacity to manage the disparate APIs of the three distinct software stacks.

3.1.2 TS4NFDI Mapping Service

The EMBL-EBI Ontology Xref Service (OxO) was initially considered a candidate for supporting SSSOM integration in the initialization phase of TS4NFDI. However, the extension of OxO in this matter was not pursued further as the maintenance status of OxO and the development of the next generation version by EBI is unclear.

However, a comprehensive examination of the requirements for mapping across consortia has been conducted through a NFDI-wide survey [16], section meetings, and hackathons, thereby providing a comprehensive view of the challenges surrounding terminology mappings. The basic service TS4NFDI is planned to address these challenges by integrating a mapping service which provides functionality to handle mappings based on SSSOM.

Consequently, the Cocoda mapping tool, which is already in use within the NFDI4Object consortium, was selected as the platform for developing and supporting SSSOM during the integration phase.

3.1.3 Incubator Dashboard

A first version of the Incubator Dashboard was part of the TS4NFDI Service Portal prototype presented in Q1/2025. It lists in total 11 incubators.

3.2 API Gateway

An initial version of the API Gateway was developed and deployed, with an adaptable modular federation model. Key service functions and technical specifications, including data flows, technologies used, and performance considerations, have been documented. This foundational work has been thoroughly reviewed to prioritize use cases for the API Gateway, service wrappers, and TSS functionalities. The resulting service documentation and data flows have been published in a GitHub repository⁶, ensuring transparency and accessibility for the community.

An essential component of this effort involved identifying and prioritizing critical API functions for the centralized system and the TSS, ensuring alignment with the NFDI consortia's requirements. An API specification document, which details the necessary functionalities and their corresponding service calls, has been made available on Zenodo [15]. A set of initial API endpoints has been defined for the central API Gateway, alongside the initial set of service wrappers for core technologies such as OLS, OntoPortal, and SKOSMOS. This specification includes details on URL format, HTTP methods, service parameters, authentication methods, and expected response formats for each endpoint.

3.2.1 API Specification and Service Wrappers

The API Gateway is central to the architecture, acting as a middleware between user interfaces and backend systems, enabling seamless access to multiple NFDI terminology services. As mentioned above an analysis of the APIs has been conducted for OLS, OntoPortal, and Skosmos.

⁶ <https://github.com/ts4nfdi/api-gateway>

The API specification is designed to support cross-domain terminology access, and widgets have been developed based on the identified use cases. For each widget, API endpoints and the necessary parameters to retrieve the relevant information are documented in the API specification. This served as the basis for developing the service wrappers that handle the necessary adaptations and ensure smooth interoperability between the various terminology services.

In order to demonstrate the approach, a federated search was enabled over seven disparate terminology services. Of these, three are based on OLS, three are based on OntoPortal, and one is based on Skosmos. It was demonstrated that the results of the federated search were accessible to machines via the API Gateway and to humans via the GUI in the TSS autocomplete widget.

3.2.2 Service Databases

The development of the service databases was started at the end of the initialisation phase in Q1/2025. The prototype of the service database contains information regarding terminology collections and users of the TS4NFDI Architecture components.

3.3 Single Sign On

The prototype of the TS4NFDI service portal was developed with a rudimentary string-based user management system. Presently, there is an absence of a comprehensive, unified single sign-on mechanism.

4. Future Developments

As the project progresses, there are several key areas that will be the focus of further expansion and enhancement. It is planned to significantly expand the capabilities of the API Gateway and Terminology Service Suite (TSS), incorporating additional terminology services and extending the functionality of existing ones. This will include the integration of more external terminology sources, such as those needed for specialized research communities, and the refinement of existing services to better meet cross-domain requirements. Subsequent extensions to the architecture will

incorporate additional services summarized in the chapters above, while ongoing refinements to the API Gateway will ensure scalability, improved performance, and greater adaptability to the evolving needs of the NFDI consortia. In alignment with our efforts to foster interoperability, the system will conform to the latest interoperability and data-sharing guidelines by aligning with standards such as the EOSC MOD-API recommendation [17].

The Mapping Service will be a central focus in future developments. The first NFDI-wide instance of Cocoda is scheduled for Q2/2025. The integration of the Cocoda mapping tool, alongside support for the Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings (SSSOM), will be expanded to provide a more robust platform for creating, curating, and managing terminology mappings.

Additional features will be introduced to support ontology alignment, ensuring that users can efficiently manage conflicting or overlapping terminologies. As mapping remains a vital tool for bridging gaps between diverse terminologies across disciplines, future enhancements will focus on improving the scalability and precision of the mapping functions to meet the growing demands of the scientific community. One of these features will be the support of entity sets. An entity set is a collection/subset of entities from (different) terminologies (see Figure 3a). The TS4NFDI Service Portal will provide a configuration panel to create and maintain entity sets and terminology collections.

Figure 3: The figure illustrates in a) a terminology collection which contains the terminologies NCBITaxon and MeSH from the terminology service SemLookP and ChEBI from the NFDI4Chem terminology service. In b) an entity set is shown. This entity set contains two entities from the terminology NCBITaxon and one entity from the terminology ChEBI.

All future developments will be driven by feedback from stakeholders, workshops, and ongoing collaboration with experts in the field. We will maintain close coordination with the NFDI consortia to ensure the evolving system continues to meet the diverse requirements of users. The inclusion of real-world use cases and feedback from terminology users will help refine the API, service wrappers, and mapping capabilities to deliver a more integrated and user-centric platform.

By advancing these core areas, including API expansion, mapping service enhancements, and stakeholder engagement, we aim to position TS4NFDI as a leading system for terminology management and interoperability, supporting the broad range of tasks and use cases required by the NFDI ecosystem. The TS4NFDI Service Portal will be accessible in Q2/2025 via <https://terminology.services.base4nfdi.de>.

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